

Ochilov A.S.

Master of Jizzak State Pedagogical Institute

Supervisor: Academician Komiljon S.T.

DISTRIBUTION OF THE GYPSOPHILUS (ALLOCHRUSA GYPSOPHILOIDES REGEL) PLANT IN JIZZAKH REGION

Annotation: Jizzakh region is distinguished by its variety of plants. The climate of the continent is unique and allows the growth of various varieties. This article discusses the distribution of the gypsophila (Allochrusa gypsophiloides Regel) plant in Jizzakh region.

Keywords: Jizzakh region, Allochrusa gypsophiloides Regel, plant, method, climate.

INTRODUCTION

Jizzakh region is a region within the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the central part of the republic. It was established on December 28, 1973. It borders the Republic of Kazakhstan and Syrdarya region in the northeast, Samarkand and Navoi regions in the southwest, and the Republic of Tajikistan in the southeast. The area is 21.2 thousand km². The population is 1,382.10 thousand people (2020). Jizzakh region has 12 rural districts (Arnasoy, Bakhmal, Dostlik, Sharof Rashidov, Zarbdor, Zafarabad, Zomin, Mirzachol, Pakhtakor, Yangiabad, Forish, Ghallaorol), 9 cities (Gagarin, Dashtabad, Dostlik, Jizzakh, Marjonbulok, Pakhtakor, Ghallaorol, Zarbdor), Zomin), 8 towns (Boston, Zafarabad, Osmat, Uchkuloch, Bogdon, Pishagar, Koytash, Eastern Star), 95 village citizens' gatherings (2001). Its center is the city of Jizzakh.

MAIN PART

Carnations (Caryophyllaceae) is a family of carnations. It consists of shrubs and annual, biennial and perennial shrubs. There are 2000 species in 80 genera on earth. 122 species belonging to 24 families grow in Uzbekistan. Leaves are simple, opposite, unbanded, flat-edged. Flowers are straight, 4-5 lobed. Sepals free or connate.

There are 4-10 stamens, 1-5 seeds, the top node, the fruit is a pod. It is distributed in the temperate region of the Northern Hemisphere. Carnation, drema, lixnis, earth soap and other species are ornamental. Yetmak, soap, echkimiya and other roots are used in preparation of kholva and various drinks. Some types of sawdust are used in the atirupa industry and medicine. 10 types of carnations are included in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Distribution:

Endemic of Pamir-Aloy and Western Tien Shan. It is found in the foothills and mountains of South Kazakhstan and Jambil regions of Kazakhstan. It grows

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

at an altitude of 400-1400 m above sea level on stony and gravelly slopes and sometimes in abandoned lands.

Distributed in the regions of Tashkent, Namangan, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya: Kurama, Chotkal, Molguzar, Nurota, Hisar, Kohitang.

Caryophyllaceae - representatives of this family are annual and perennial shrubs. Their stems are cylindrical, with false dichotomous branching. The leaves are simple and opposite, sessile, sometimes membranous. Their flowers are straight, colored singly or in dichazy bunches. Most of the time, it has 2 sexes, florets, it is usually arranged in the form of five, with 5 circles. The saffron is divided into sepals and crowns, sometimes it has a simple safflower. 5 rose petals. Sepals are jointed or free, with 4-5 teeth. Petals are 4-5, alternating with the teeth of the calyx. When paternity is 5-10 by 10, paternities in the outer circle are located in front of the crowns. Mother has 1, 2, 3, 5, 4 fruits. The node is upper, single-celled. The fruit is a pod or a nut, sometimes a dry berry-fruit. The seeds are perspermous. The bag opens from the teeth at the end. The presence of saponins in the vegetative organs, especially in the underground part, is a characteristic feature of representatives of this family. This family consists of 80 genera and about 20,000 species and is widely distributed in all parts of the globe, mostly in the northern hemisphere, in the Mediterranean regions of Australia and Africa. 24 genera and 130 species grow wild in the flora of Uzbekistan. The carnation family is divided into 2 families depending on whether the calyx leaves grow freely or together.

1. The starfish family - Alsinoideae. This family includes *S. Neglecta* and *Holosteum*. The sepals of the members of this family are free, and the fruits are small or nut-like. They are annual and perennial mesophytic plants.

2. Boritikandoshcha family. (*Silenoideae*). Representatives of this family have fused sepals, corollas are banded, often there is an additional corolla consisting of stamens at the place where the corolla band passes to the plate. This family includes carnations (*Dianthus*), *Acanthophyllum*, and *Yypsophila*.

Carnation genus-(*Dianthus*). These are perennial herbs, sometimes sedges. The flowers are 1 or umbel-like, located in dichaza type inflorescences. The calyx is tubular, 5-toothed. The petals are 5, long-banded, different colors, and the tip is toothed or serrated. Paternity is 10. The mother has two leaves. The fruit is a bag with many seeds. 10 species grow wild in Uzbekistan. It is also grown in houses and flower gardens. Chinese carnation (*D. Chinensis*), a one-year plant native to China, as well as Turkish carnation (*D. Barbatus*) and Dutch carnation (*D. Coryorhylus*) imported from Central and Western Europe, are widely cultivated.

Importance of cloves in the economy. The presence of strong toxic saponins or glycoside saponins is one of the main characteristics of this family. Such saponins accumulate a lot in the roots of *gypsophila*. Several species are planted as decorative plants. For this purpose, 70 types of cloves are grown. Yetmak has

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

been cultivated in Uzbekistan as a technical plant. There are no good fodder species among them. But there are some representatives who are medicine.

CONCLUSION

In the Jizzakh region, the seeds are light brown, almost spherical, slightly flattened on the sides, ripen in early August, but do not disintegrate until autumn. The root is rhizome-like, sometimes fusiform, twisted, up to 2 m long and more, weighing up to 12 kg. Several branched lateral roots emerge from the tap root. Thorny thorn (Turkistan soap root) does not have the ability to regenerate after its roots are dug up, so the natural thickets of this plant do not regenerate after harvesting.

REFERENCES

1. Integration of science, education and production in the development of modern biological education. April 8, 2022.
2. Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute Norkulova Munura (article) Tashkent 2021
3. Botany, study guide. A. Matkarimova, T. Makhkamov, M. Makhmudova, Khamidjon Azizov, G. Vaisova Tashkent "Teacher" 2018 p. 353
4. Рашидов Диловар Нажмиддинович, & Холбоев Йигитали Авганович (2022). КОРХОНА ВА ТАШКИЛОТЛАРДА ИЖТИМОЙ ҲИМОЯГА МУҲТОЖ ШАХСЛАР УЧУН ИШ ҶУРИЛАРИНИ ЙЎНАЛИШЛАР КЕСИМИДА ЗАХИРАЛАШНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ. Трансформация моделей корпоративного управления в условиях цифровой экономики, 1 (1), 73-78. doi: 10.24412/cl-36899-2022-1-73-78
From the website <https://ziyonet.uz/>.

WORDLY
KNOWLEDGE